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Welcome to Ash tree genomes

This website hosts ash genome data to assist scientists in the search for genes that may confer resistance to ash dieback (*Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*) and the emerald ash borer (*Agrilus planipennis*).

Scientists at Queen Mary, University of London (QMUL) in [Richard Buggs' lab](#) have sequenced the genome of the European ash tree (*Fraxinus excelsior*), funded by an urgency grant awarded by the Natural Environment Research Council in 2013. The ash genome and associated data have now been published in *Nature*. The paper is available open access [here](#).

The tree sequenced was the result of self-pollination of a tree growing in woodland in Oxfordshire. The controlled self-pollination of the parent tree was carried out by [Dr David Boshier](#) of Oxford University. The offspring from this self-pollination are growing at Paradise Wood in Oxfordshire, owned by the [Earth Trust](#), and managed by Jo Clark. Tissue was collected from one of these trees in January 2013 and DNA was extracted from it by Jasmin Zohren (funded by MSC ITN "Intercrossing")

at QMUL. Using flow cytometry, we estimated the 1C genome size of the tree to be 877 Mbp.

Raw DNA sequence data for the British ash genome were generated by [Eurofins](#), and the data was assembled by Lizzy Sollars (funded by MSC ITN "Intercrossing") and Richard Buggs at QMUL, in collaboration with [CLCbio](#), using open access and proprietary software. Assembly and analysis of the genome is being carried out on the [QMUL-High Performance Computing](#) MidPlus cluster, and servers at CLCbio.

Since 2014 we have collaborated with [The Genome Analysis Centre](#) in Norwich to improve and annotate the genome assembly. Full structural annotations are available for the latest assembly under the "Data" tab.

Now based at both QMUL and Royal Botanic Gardens Kew, we have sequenced the genomes of nearly 30 other ash species from around the world. Most of these genomes have now been published in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#). This work was funded by the LWEC Tree Health and Plant Biosecurity Initiative Phase 2 Grant, BB/L012162/1 funded jointly by a grant from BBSRC, Defra, ESRC, the Forestry Commission, NERC and the Scottish Government.

The fight against ash dieback - BBC London

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Outreach

News articles, radio podcasts and videos

Date	Programme	Link
30/09/18	BBC One TV London News	Youtube
03/01/18	Babbage Podcast (The Economist)	Trees take a bough
14/06/17	Nacked Scientists	Can genes save our trees?
12/04/17	Babbage Podcast (The Economist)	What can science do for my garden?
26/12/16	BBC	Ash tree genome sequenced for first time
26/12/16	Guardian	British ash trees may resist dieback disease, research reveals
26/12/16	Daily Mail	Trees resistant to killer fungus could be grown in Britain
26/12/16	Daily Express	Ash trees could be saved from killer disease after UK study cracks genetic code
13/01/16	BBSRC	Screening technique to reinforce fight against ash dieback
08/07/15	Journal of Experimental Biology Youtube Channel	Genomics of <i>Fraxinus</i>
07/10/14	BBC News Channel	Interview on ash dieback
22/06/14	The Conversation	Despite the lush summer leaves, our trees are under attack
07/06/14	Sunday Telegraph	Ash dieback is now 'unstoppable', ecologists warn
15/05/14	France 24	Talking Europe
01/10/13	Planet Earth Podcast	Using genetics to fight ash dieback
27/09/13	BBC Radio 4	Ashes to Ashes
26/09/13	BBC News	Ash trees also face insect threat
26/09/13	CLC bio press release	CLC bio and UK scientists assemble ash tree genome
23/09/13	BBC News	Scientists map UK ash tree genome
12/6/13	BBC1 News at One, BBC1 News at Six	Interview on ash dieback
Summer 2013	Planet Earth	The last stand?
5/2/13	Planet Earth	Using genetics to save the ash tree
21/12/12	Today programme, BBC Radio 4	Interview on ash dieback
21/12/12	Good Morning Scotland, BBC Scotland	Interview on ash dieback
21/12/12	Laurence Reed Show, BBC Cornwall	Interview on ash dieback
21/12/12	Planet Earth Online	New genetics project could help save the ash tree

FRAXBACK London Conference

[Programme](#) | [Conference book](#) | [FRAXBACK website](#)

A one day conference, "Ash dieback in Europe: elaborating guidelines and strategies for sustainable management" was held on 29th November 2013 at The Linnean Society of London, Burlington House, Piccadilly, London, W1J 0BF. Speakers included scientists working on ash dieback in France, Sweden, Denmark, Norway, Germany, Belgium, Latvia, Austria and Lithuania. This conference was sold out and was thus webcast at www.fraxback.eu. This meeting was supported and organised by the European Cooperation in Science and Technology action [FRAXBACK](#).

Videos: [Session 1](#) | [Session 2](#) | [Session 3](#) | [Session 4](#)

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Data

Please follow the links for data downloads:

[Genome assemblies for *Fraxinus excelsior*](#)

[Transcriptomes & Proteome for *Fraxinus excelsior*](#)

[Genome assemblies for worldwide *Fraxinus* species](#)

DNA and RNA read files for *Fraxinus excelsior* can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB4958](#)

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Genome Assemblies for *Fraxinus excelsior*

BATG-0.5

 Released 29/10/2015 and published in *Nature* in January 2017, assembled by Lizzy Sollars. Paired reads with insert sizes of: 200bp, 300bp, 500b, 5kb and 454 reads were used to build contigs in CLC Genomics Workbench. Scaffolding was performed using SSPACE with all paired reads (those mentioned in addition to Long Jumping Distance libraries of 3, 8, 20 and 40 kbp). Gaps in the scaffolds were closed using GapCloser and further joining of scaffolds was done using PBJelly with the 454 reads. A major update in this version is that the chloroplast and mitochondrial genomes have been extracted from the nuclear genome; both are located at the end of the assembly file. The chloroplast genome is contained in one contig of 155,498 bp, named 'Cp1'. The mitochondrial genome is present as a draft version in 26 contigs, named 'Mt#' (1-26). Stats for the mitochondrial genome are shown in the table below, along with full stats of the whole genome assembly.

	Contigs	Scaffolds	Mt Genome
Number	118,959	89,514	26
Total size	718.4 Mbp	867.5 Mbp	580,788 bp
Longest	209,591	884,900 bp	184,534 bp
Shortest	326	326 bp	326 bp
Number > 1K nt	68,628	40,777	25
Number > 10K nt	18,860	10,151	11
Number > 100K nt	210	2,522	1
Mean size	6,039	9,691	22,338
Median size	1,228	911	6,487
N50 length	25,341	103,995 bp	60,627
L50 count	7,922	2,389	3
A	32.87%	27.22%	27.49%
C	17.13%	14.19%	22.50%
G	17.14%	14.19%	22.29%
T	32.85%	27.2%	27.67%
N	0.00%	17.19%	0.04%
CEGMA complete hits		208 genes (84%)	
CEGMA partial hits		238 genes (96 %)	

BATG-0.4-CLCbioSSPACE

 Released 11/11/2013, assembled by Lizzy Sollars. Since the last assembly release, we have improved the contiguity of the assembly by scaffolding the CLC contigs together using all paired read files, and lowering the SSPACE parameter '-k' (number of paired reads linking two contigs) to 7. This reduced the

number of N nucleotides inserted into gaps between contigs, and SOAP's GapCloser reduced the number of N's still further.

	Contigs	Scaffolds
Number	120,753	89,285
Total size	706,623,136 bp	875,243,685 bp
Longest	219,535 bp	696,341 bp
Shortest	500 bp	500 bp
Number > 1K nt	69,334	39,713
Number > 10K nt	19,491	10,818
Number > 100K nt	123	2,484
Mean size	5,852 bp	9,803 bp
Median size	1,246 bp	878 bp
N50 length	22,633 bp	98,766 bp
L50 count	8,788	2,526
A	32.87 %	26.54 %
C	17.13 %	13.83 %
G	17.14 %	13.84 %
T	32.85 %	26.52 %
N	0.00 %	19.27 %
CEGMA complete hits		220 genes (89 %)
CEGMA partial hits		241 genes (97 %)

BATG-0.3-CLCbioSSPACE

 Released 23/09/2013, assembled by Lizzy Sollars. This represents a significant improvement on our previous release: the total size is now closer to the 877 Mbp size of the genome measured by flow cytometry, and the N50 length is five times longer than the N50 of the previous release. Reads from paired libraries of insert sizes: 200bp, 300bp, 500bp, and Long-Jumping Distance (LJD) libraries of 3kb, 8kb, 20kb and 40kb, were trimmed to a minimum Phred quality score of 20, a minimum length of 50bp, and were also trimmed of any adaptor and repetitive telomere sequences. Reads were assembled de novo using CLC bio with a word size (k-mer) of 50, into contigs with a minimum length of 500bp. The LJD pairs and 454 contigs assembled using Newbler (BATG-0.1-Newbler) were used as guidance reads to resolve ambiguities in the de bruijn graphs. Contigs were then scaffolded using the stand-alone tool SSSPACE, and gaps in the scaffolds were closed using the GapCloser program from SOAP.

	Contigs	Scaffolds
Number	180,582	142,021
Total size	719,081,378 bp	982,425,322 bp
Longest	174,200 bp	560,578 bp
Shortest	500 bp	500 bp
Number > 1K nt	96,147 (53.2%)	60,768 (42.8%)
Number > 10K nt	19,217 (10.6%)	14,113 (9.9%)
Mean size	3,982 bp	6,917 bp
Median size	1,084 bp	866 bp
N50 length	14,766 bp	68,494 bp
L50 count	12,859	3,996
A	32.89 %	24.07 %
C	17.13 %	12.54 %
G	17.13 %	12.54 %

	Contigs	Scaffolds
T	32.85 %	24.05 %
N	0.00 %	26.81 %
CEGMA complete hits		214 genes (86 %)
CEGMA partial hits		242 genes (98 %)

BATG-0.2-CLCbio

 Released 11/06/2013, assembled by Lizzy Sollars. Illumina 100bp reads were trimmed on two parameters: bases with a phred score of less than 15 were trimmed from the ends, and reads less than 50 bp long were then discarded from the dataset. Paired reads from a 200bp insert library were joined if they overlapped by at least 20bp. A de novo assembly was performed with the CLC assembler using a word size (k-mer) of 64, using trimmed reads from 200bp, 300bp, and 500bp insert size Illumina libraries to construct the de bruijn graph. Reads from an 8Kb LJD library and the 454 contigs (assembly BATG-0.1-Newbler) were used to resolve ambiguities in the graph. All paired-end reads were used for scaffolding. The gaps in the scaffolds were then filled using the GapCloser program from SOAP, which approximately halved the number of 'N' nucleotides.

	Contigs	Scaffolds
Number	358,807	283,188
Total size	1,214,865,037 bp	1,469,483,817 bp
Longest	141,171 bp	221,212 bp
Shortest	56 bp	344 bp
Number > 1K nt	197,676 (55.1%)	163,534 (57.7%)
Number > 10K nt	33,093 (9.2%)	45,273 (16.0%)
Mean size	3,386 bp	5,189 bp
Median size	1,156 bp	1,266 bp
N50 length	9,493 bp	14,228 bp
L50 count	35,755	30,458
A	32.86 %	27.16 %
C	17.14 %	14.17 %
G	17.13 %	14.16 %
T	32.86 %	27.17 %
N	0.01 %	17.34 %
CEGMA complete hits		189 genes (76 %)
CEGMA partial hits		237 genes (96 %)

BATG-0.1-Newbler

 Released 22/04/2013. This is the first genome assembly release of the British Ash Tree Genome project. It is based on 4.3X coverage of the ash genome by Roche 454 sequencing, and assembled using Newbler and the CLC Genome Finishing Module by Lizzy Sollars. The options used in Newbler to make this assembly were: '-sl 32', '-urt', '-m', '-e 5'. Ten other assemblies with different options were carried out in Newbler, and this assembly was selected on the basis of highest contig N50 length and highest number of complete hits of core eukaryote genes using CEGMA (a search for 248 ultra-conserved core eukaryote genes). Statistics for this assembly are as follows:

Number of contigs	417,760
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Total size of contigs	618,360,624 bp
Longest contig	51,710 bp
Shortest contig	100 bp
Number of contigs > 1K nt	209,375 (50.1%)
Number of contigs > 10K nt	1549 (0.4%)
Mean contig size	1,480 bp
Median contig size	1,004 bp
N50 contig length	2,412 bp
L50 contig count	73,440
A	32.60 %
C	17.38 %
G	17.15 %
T	32.86 %
N	0.00 %
CEGMA complete hits	127 genes (51 %)
CEGMA partial hits	220 genes (89 %)

We ask all users of these assemblies to adhere to a data usage policy that can be found [here](#).

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Transcriptomes & Proteome of *Fraxinus excelsior*

Annotation Version 4 (TGAC v2) - on assembly BATG-0.5

Released 08/02/16 in collaboration with The Genome Analysis Centre

Annotation	File	Notes
Full Annotation	GFF	GFF file of all gene, mRNA, CDS, 3'UTR and 5'UTR annotations (all isoforms), excluding transposable elements
Transposable Elements	GFF	GFF file of transposable elements.
cDNA Fasta	FASTA	FASTA file of all cDNA (transcript) sequences (all isoforms).
CDS Fasta	FASTA	FASTA file of all CDS DNA sequences (all isoforms).
Proteome	FASTA	FASTA file of all CDS peptide sequences (all isoforms).
Longest transcript: Annotation	GFF	GFF file of all genes, and only mRNA, CDS, 3'UTR and 5'UTR annotations for the longest isoform.
Longest transcript: cDNA	FASTA	FASTA file of cDNA (transcript) sequences (longest isoform per gene only).
Longest transcript: CDS	FASTA	FASTA file of CDS DNA sequences, (longest isoform per gene only)
Longest transcript: Proteome	FASTA	FASTA file of CDS peptide sequences (longest isoform per gene only)
Functional annotation	TSV	GO and Interproscan terms associated with each gene

Annotation Version 3 (TGAC v2) - on assembly BATG-0.4

Released 26/02/15 in collaboration with The Genome Analysis Centre

Annotation	File	Notes
Full Annotation	GFF	GFF file of all gene, mRNA, CDS, 3'UTR and 5'UTR annotations. (all isoforms).
cDNA Fasta	FASTA	FASTA file of all cDNA (transcript) sequences (all isoforms).
CDS Fasta	FASTA	FASTA file of all CDS DNA sequences (all isoforms).
Proteome	FASTA	FASTA file of all CDS peptide sequences (all isoforms).
Functional annotation	TSV	GO and Interproscan terms associated with all genes (all isoforms).
Longest transcript: Annotation	GFF	GFF file of all genes, and only mRNA, CDS, 3'UTR and 5'UTR annotations for the longest isoform.
Longest transcript: cDNA	FASTA	FASTA file of cDNA (transcript) sequences (longest isoform per gene only).
Longest transcript: CDS	FASTA	FASTA file of CDS DNA sequences, (longest isoform per gene only)
Longest transcript: Proteome	FASTA	FASTA file of CDS peptide sequences (longest isoform per gene only)

Longest transcript: Functional annotation	TSV	GO and Interproscan terms associated with longest isoform of each gene.
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Methods V3 (BATG-0.4)

A three-way pipeline was used to predict genes *ab initio* consisting of 1). MAKER, 2). Augustus (without RNA-seq data), and 3). Augustus (with RNA-seq data). The following data were fed into the pipeline: RNA reads from five samples shown below in Annotation Version 2, the gene models produced in Version 2 by Lizzy Sollars, a repeat-masked genome produced by Laura Kelly at QMUL, and alignments of protein sequences from eight other plant species. The pipeline was run by Gemy Kaithokottil and David Swarbreck at TGAC. Evidence Modeller was then used to select the most accurate structure for each gene, as each of the three methods will predict slightly different gene structures. Filtering was performed using PASA. Resulting genes were annotated using BLAST, GO terms and Interproscan. This updated version predicts more genes than the previous version, as the previous relied solely on RNA data and therefore only those genes that were expressed at the time of RNA extraction.

This annotation can be visualised in the JBrowse tool on this website, and also on [gbrowse](#) hosted at TGAC.

Annotation Version 2 - BATG-0.4:

Sample	GFF3	FASTA	No. of genes/proteins	Notes
Selfed tree leaf	S_L1	S_L1	27,360	Assembled transcriptome of leaf tissue from the selfed tree (gz compressed).
Mother tree leaf	M_L1	M_L1	24,473	Assembled transcriptome of leaf tissue from the mother tree (gz compressed).
Mother tree cambium	M_C1	M_C1	27,368	Assembled transcriptome of cambium tissue from the mother tree (gz compressed).
Mother tree root	M_R2	M_R2	28,275	Assembled transcriptome of root tissue from the mother tree (gz compressed).
Mother tree flower	M_F1	M_F1	29,562	Assembled transcriptome of flower tissue from the mother tree (gz compressed).
All samples combined	Bulk	Bulk	36,944	Tar archive of the five files above.
All samples		Unigenes	36,944	The longest transcript per gene (gz compressed). Filtered on coverage.
All samples		Proteome	36,893	Predicted protein coding sequence for each unigene (gz compressed)
All samples unfiltered		Unigenes	41,521	Longest transcript per gene, before filtering.
All samples unfiltered		mRNA	72,139	All mRNA transcripts, before filtering.

Methods (v2)

RNA was extracted by Jasmin Zohren from 5 tissues: leaf, cambium, root, and flower of the 'mother' tree, and from leaf tissue of the 'selfed' tree (the individual for which we have provided a [reference genome sequence](#)). These were sequenced using Illumina HiSeq paired-end technology. Adapter sequences were removed from the reads, which were then also quality trimmed to a minimum Phred score of 20 and minimum length of 50bp. The transcriptome data were assembled by Lizzy Sollars using the [CLC Transcript Discovery Plugin](#). RNA-seq reads were mapped to the BATG_0.4 reference genome using the Large Gap Read Mapper (accounts for intron sequences in the reference), and the location of genes and mRNA transcripts were predicted using the Transcript Discovery tool. Reads were then mapped back to the transcripts and those with an average coverage of less than 5 were filtered out.

The GFF3 files above contain the locations of genes, transcripts, exons, and introns for each tissue, and the FASTA files contain the sequences of each mRNA transcript. The 'bulk' files are tar archives of the five separate sample files. The unigenes files comprises one transcript per gene, with all samples combined, i.e. a 'complete' reference ash transcriptome. The longest gene in each location was selected for this file, regardless of which sample it originated from. The proteome file contains one protein sequence for each gene, predicted from running a command-line version of OrfPredictor. The input for this was the unigene file and its resulting output of a BLASTx search against all plant proteins in the RefSeq database.

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Worldwide ash species genomes

The v0.1 assemblies for the majority of taxa listed below have now been published in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; if referring to these assemblies please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Since March 2017 we have been uploading early access data for these ash species from around the world under the Fort Lauderdale agreement. Some of these data have now been published; see the pages for individual species for further details.

Update 27th April 2020: We have amended some of the taxon names following redetermination of some individuals used for genome sequencing (for further details see [here](#)); the original names the genome assemblies were first released under are given in parentheses.

[*Fraxinus albicans*](#)

[*Fraxinus americana*](#)

[*Fraxinus angustifolia* subsp. *angustifolia*](#)

[*Fraxinus angustifolia* subsp. *oxycarpa*](#)

[*Fraxinus angustifolia* subsp. *syriaca*](#)

[*Fraxinus anomala*](#)

[*Fraxinus apertisquamifera*](#)

[*Fraxinus baroniana*](#)

Fraxinus biltmoreana (syn. *F. americana* var. *biltmoreana*)

Fraxinus chinensis subsp. *rhyncophylla*

[*Fraxinus cuspidata*](#)

[*Fraxinus dipetala*](#)

[*Fraxinus excelsior*](#) [already published]

[*Fraxinus floribunda*](#)

[*Fraxinus goodingii*](#)

[*Fraxinus greggii*](#)

[*Fraxinus griffithii*](#)

Fraxinus lanuginosa

[*Fraxinus latifolia*](#)

[*Fraxinus mandshurica*](#)

[*Fraxinus nigra*](#)

[*Fraxinus ornus*](#)

[*Fraxinus paxiana*](#)

[*Fraxinus pennsylvanica*](#) [accession 56.0410] (previously labelled as *Fraxinus caroliniana*)

[*Fraxinus pennsylvanica*](#) [accession PE_00248]

[*Fraxinus pennsylvanica*](#) [accession PE_48]

[*Fraxinus platypoda*](#)

Fraxinus profunda

[*Fraxinus quadrangulata*](#)

[Fraxinus sieboldiana](#)

[Fraxinus uhdei](#)

[Fraxinus velutina](#)

[Fraxinus xanthoxyloides](#)

[Fraxinus sp. 1973-6204](#) (previously labelled as *Fraxinus bungeana*)

[Fraxinus sp. D2006-0159](#) (previously labelled as *Fraxinus chinensis* [subsp. *chinensis*?])

This work is funded by Living with Environmental Change: Tree Health and Plant Biosecurity Initiative - Phase 2 Grant, BB/L012162/1 to Richard Buggs, funded jointly by a grant from BBSRC, Defra, ESRC, the Forestry Commission, NERC and the Scottish Government. This project has also received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 660003.

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Fraxinus albicans genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus albicans*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 11th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus albicans* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 68x on the Illumina HiSeq platform. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	300,217
Assembly size (Mbp)	712
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	933
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	121,939
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	16,934
Largest scaffold (bp)	195,698
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.6
N50 (bp)	7,428
L50	26,839
Ns (%)	0
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1230 [85.4%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1041 [72.3%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	189 [13.1%]

Fragmented BUSCOs	92 [6.4%]
Missing BUSCOs	118 [8.2%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#).
The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

[Proceed to data download](#)

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Fraxinus americana genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus americana*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 11th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus americana* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 40x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	357,129
Assembly size (Mbp)	642.6
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	886
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	143,635
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	9,191
Largest scaffold (bp)	195,469
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.4
N50 (bp)	4,583
L50	38,222
Ns (%)	0.01
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,147 [79.7%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	986 [68.5%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	161 [11.2%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	131 [9.1%]
Missing BUSCOs	162 [11.3%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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Fraxinus angustifolia subsp. angustifolia genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus angustifolia* subsp. *angustifolia*, assembled by Laura Kelly. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 30th March 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus angustifolia* subsp. *angustifolia* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 48x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for a library made from total genomic DNA, with an approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. No scaffolding or gap filling has been performed.

Assembly statistics

Number of contigs	489,825
Assembly size (Mbp)	693
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	812
# contig > 1000 bp	168,107
# contig > 10000 bp	6,661
Largest contig (bp)	124,647
Smallest contig (bp)	200
GC (%)	35.5
N50 (bp)	3,264
L50	53,930
Ns (%)	0
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,001 [69.5%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	861 [59.8%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	140 [9.7%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	196 [13.6%]
Missing BUSCOs	243 [16.9%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

Any analyses involving data are included in this data usage policy, including annotation of genes, identification of sets of genomic features such as genes, gene families, regulatory elements, repeat structures, GC content, etc., and whole-genome comparisons of regions of among-species conservation. Also included are uses of the genome data as a reference for transcriptomic analyses (RNA seq, bisulfite seq, chip seq or similar). Interested parties are encouraged to contact the principal investigator if they wish to discuss the possibility of collaborative publication of such analyses.

The data may be freely downloaded and used by all who respect the restrictions in the previous paragraphs. In the period before the peer-reviewed journal publication the assembly and raw sequence reads should not be redistributed or repackaged without permission of Richard Buggs.

Once moved to unreserved status, the data will be freely available for any subsequent use.

By downloading these data you are agreeing to the terms outlined above.

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Fraxinus angustifolia subsp. oxycarpa genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus angustifolia* subsp. *oxycarpa*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 11th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus angustifolia* subsp. *oxycarpa* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 38x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie ±40%). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	413,147
Assembly size (Mbp)	714.3
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	c.846
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	175,656
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	8,004
Largest scaffold (bp)	191,109
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.1
N50 (bp)	3,952
L50	49,086
Ns (%)	0.01
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,083 [75.2%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	949 [65.9%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	134 [9.3%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	174 [12.1%]
Missing BUSCOs	183 [12.7%]

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Fraxinus angustifolia subsp. syriaca genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus angustifolia* subsp. *syriaca*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 11th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus angustifolia* subsp. *syriaca* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 37x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie ±40%). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	323,049
Assembly size (Mbp)	586
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	792
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	137,108
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	7,353
Largest scaffold (bp)	150,017
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.4
N50 (bp)	4,357
L50	37,150
Ns (%)	0.01
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,085 [75.3%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	958 [66.5%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	127 [8.8%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	170 [11.8%]
Missing BUSCOs	185 [12.8%]

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Fraxinus anomala genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus anomala*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 12th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus anomala* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 58x on the Illumina HiSeq platform. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	205,647
Assembly size (Mbp)	655.8
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	c.713
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	97,393
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	18,391
Largest scaffold (bp)	181,166
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	33.8
N50 (bp)	10,033
L50	18,306
Ns (%)	0.09
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,266 [87.9%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,068 [74.2%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	198 [13.8%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	69 [4.8%]
Missing BUSCOs	105 [7.3%]

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Fraxinus apertisquamifera genome Assembly

Assembled in 2018. The genome of *Fraxinus apertisquamifera* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 45x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for a library made from total genomic DNA, with an approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly.

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Fraxinus baroniana genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus baroniana*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 12th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus baroniana* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 52x on the Illumina HiSeq platform. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	314,574
Assembly size (Mbp)	716.5
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	934
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	140,029
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	14,408
Largest scaffold (bp)	183,985
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.28
N50 (bp)	6,176
L50	32,279
Ns (%)	0.12
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,183 [82.2%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,012 [70.3%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	171 [11.9%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	126 [8.8%]
Missing BUSCOs	131 [9.1%]

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Fraxinus cuspidata genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus cuspidata*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 12th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus cuspidata* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 59x on the Illumina HiSeq platform. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	133,719
Assembly size (Mbp)	623.2
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	c.898
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	63,190
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	19,871
Largest scaffold (bp)	155,167
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	33.7
N50 (bp)	16,666
L50	10,801
Ns (%)	0.07
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,285 [89.2%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,072 [74.4%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	213 [14.8%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	60 [4.2%]
Missing BUSCOs	95 [6.6%]

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Fraxinus dipetala genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus dipetala*, assembled by Laura Kelly. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 4th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus dipetala* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 57x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for a library made from total genomic DNA, with an approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. No scaffolding or gap filling has been performed.

Assembly statistics

Number of contigs	360,749
Assembly size (Mbp)	586
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	805
# contig > 1000 bp	135,751
# contig > 10000 bp	6,991
Largest contig (bp)	131,964
Smallest contig (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.4
N50 (bp)	4,042
L50	39,126
Ns (%)	0
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1024 [71.1%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	879 [61.0%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	145 [10.1%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	204 [14.2%]
Missing BUSCOs	212 [14.7%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession PRJEB20151. The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

Any analyses involving data are included in this data usage policy, including annotation of genes, identification of sets of genomic features such as genes, gene families, regulatory elements, repeat structures, GC content, etc., and whole-genome comparisons of regions of among-species conservation. Also included are uses of the genome data as a reference for transcriptomic analyses (RNA seq, bisulfite seq, chip seq or similar). Interested parties are encouraged to contact the principal investigator if they wish to discuss the possibility of collaborative publication of such analyses.

The data may be freely downloaded and used by all who respect the restrictions in the previous paragraphs. In the period before the peer-reviewed journal publication the assembly and raw sequence reads should not be redistributed or repackaged without permission of Richard Buggs.

Once moved to unreserved status, the data will be freely available for any subsequent use.

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Fraxinus floribunda genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus floribunda*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 12th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus floribunda* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 57x on the Illumina HiSeq platform. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	343,180
Assembly size (Mbp)	710.1
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	963
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	143,531
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	13,151
Largest scaffold (bp)	239,794
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.4
N50 (bp)	5,677
L50	34,552
Ns (%)	0.1
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,173 [81.5%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,003 [69.7%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	170 [11.8%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	131 [9.1%]
Missing BUSCOs	136 [9.4%]

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Fraxinus goodingii genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus goodingii*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 23rd February 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus goodingii* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 54x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters, incorporating data from mate-pair libraries with 3kb and 10kb insert sizes. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	452,616
Assembly size (Mbp)	904.2
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	969
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	66,509
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	19,606
Largest scaffold (bp)	464,370
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	33.17
N50 (bp)	26,688
L50	8,711
Ns (%)	8.4
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,264 [87.8%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,043 [72.4%]

Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	221 [15.3%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	48 [3.3%]
Missing BUSCOs	128 [8.9%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#).
The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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Fraxinus greggii genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus greggii*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 11th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus greggii* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 29x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie ±40%). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	430,537
Assembly size (Mbp)	694.3
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	843
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	154,298
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	9,506
Largest scaffold (bp)	113,384
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.4
N50 (bp)	4,303
L50	42,589
Ns (%)	0.18
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,127 [78.3%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	972 [67.5%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	155 [10.8%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	156 [10.8%]
Missing BUSCOs	157 [10.9%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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Fraxinus griffithii genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus griffithii*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 11th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus griffithii* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 43x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	349,639
Assembly size (Mbp)	739.5
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	c.972
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	124,082
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	17,169
Largest scaffold (bp)	217,334
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	35.4
N50 (bp)	7,160
L50	28,553
Ns (%)	0.16
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,145 [79.5%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,001 [69.5%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	144 [10%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	106 [7.4%]
Missing BUSCOs	189 [13.1%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/record/PRJEB20151). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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Fraxinus latifolia genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus latifolia*, assembled by Laura Kelly. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 5th May 2020. The genome of *Fraxinus latifolia* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 44x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for a library made from total genomic DNA, with an approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. No scaffolding or gap filling has been performed.

Assembly statistics

Number of contigs	520,236
Assembly size (Mbp)	720
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	935
# contig > 1000 bp	196,922
# contig > 10000 bp	4,880
Largest contig (bp)	120,176
Smallest contig (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.5
N50 (bp)	2,755
L50	66,853
Ns (%)	0
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,019 [70.8%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	879 [61.0%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	140 [9.7%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	184 [12.8%]
Missing BUSCOs	237 [16.5%]

For v0.1, the assembly and DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#).

For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

Any analyses involving data are included in this data usage policy, including annotation of genes, identification of sets of genomic features such as genes, gene families, regulatory elements, repeat structures, GC content, etc., and whole-genome comparisons of regions of among-species conservation. Also included are uses of the genome data as a reference for transcriptomic analyses (RNA seq, bisulfite seq, chip seq or similar). Interested parties are encouraged to contact the principal investigator if they wish to discuss the possibility of collaborative publication of such analyses.

The data may be freely downloaded and used by all who respect the restrictions in the previous paragraphs. In the period before the peer-reviewed journal publication the assembly and raw sequence reads should not be redistributed or repackaged without permission of Richard Buggs.

Once moved to unreserved status, the data will be freely available for any subsequent use.

By downloading these data you are agreeing to the terms outlined above.

Version 0.2 Assembly

This version includes 800bp insert libraries and was assembled in 2018 by Josiah Seaman using the same pipeline and methodology. The new assemblies have higher contiguity, however annotations from v0.1 assemblies are not compatible with v0.2 coordinates. Other than the additional sequence library all other sequence sources and methods are identical.

[Download v0.2 Assembly](#)

[v0.2 Annotation](#)

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Fraxinus mandshurica genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus mandshurica*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 23rd February 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus mandshurica* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 44x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters, incorporating data from mate-pair libraries with 3kb and 10kb insert sizes. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	297,505
Assembly size (Mbp)	830.5
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	899
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	60,154
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	18,867
Largest scaffold (bp)	310,417
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	30.3
N50 (bp)	30,144
L50	7,359
Ns (%)	13.4
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,293 [89.8%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,071 [74.4%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	222 [15.4%]

Fragmented BUSCOs	45 [3.1%]
Missing BUSCOs	102 [7.1%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

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Fraxinus nigra genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus nigra*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 11th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus nigra* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 43x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	301,269
Assembly size (Mbp)	616.4
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	c.976
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	124,761
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	10,948
Largest scaffold (bp)	159,265
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.5
N50 (bp)	5,611
L50	31,215
Ns (%)	0.23
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,144 [79.4%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	990 [68.8%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	154 [10.7%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	138 [9.6%]
Missing BUSCOs	158 [11%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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Fraxinus ornus genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus ornus*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 23rd February 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus ornus* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 46x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters, incorporating data from mate-pair libraries with 3kb and 10kb insert sizes. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	417,940
Assembly size (Mbp)	855.1
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	1,043
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	77,211
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	20,212
Largest scaffold (bp)	367,815
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	29.97
N50 (bp)	21,026
L50	10,470
Ns (%)	13.4
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,293 [89.8%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,067 [74.1%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	226 [15.7%]

Fragmented BUSCOs	53 [3.7%]
Missing BUSCOs	94 [6.5%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

Any analyses involving data are included in this data usage policy, including annotation of genes, identification of sets of genomic features such as genes, gene families, regulatory elements, repeat structures, GC content, etc., and whole-genome comparisons of regions of among-species conservation. Also included are uses of the genome data as a reference for transcriptomic analyses (RNA seq, bisulfite seq, chip seq or similar). Interested parties are encouraged to contact the the principal investigator if they wish to discuss the possibility of collaborative publication of such analyses.

The data may be freely downloaded and used by all who respect the restrictions in the previous paragraphs. In the period before the peer-reviewed journal publication the assembly and raw sequence reads should not be redistributed or repackaged without permission of Richard Buggs.

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Fraxinus paxiana genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus paxiana*, assembled by Laura Kelly. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 4th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus paxiana* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 39x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for a library made from total genomic DNA, with an approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. No scaffolding or gap filling has been performed.

Assembly statistics

Number of contigs	489,587
Assembly size (Mbp)	628
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	1,144
# contig > 1000 bp	170,538
# contig > 10000 bp	3,055
Largest contig (bp)	92,133
Smallest contig (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.8
N50 (bp)	2,646
L50	63,137
Ns (%)	0
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	948 [65.8%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	835 [58.0%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	113 [7.8%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	241 [16.7%]
Missing BUSCOs	251 [17.4%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

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Fraxinus pennsylvanica genome assembly [accession 56.0410]

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* [accession 56.0410] (previously labelled as *Fraxinus caroliniana*), assembled by Laura Kelly. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 30th March 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 44x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for a library made from total genomic DNA, with an approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. No scaffolding or gap filling has been performed.

Update 27th April 2020: the species name has been changed from *Fraxinus caroliniana* to *F. pennsylvanica* following redetermination of the individual used for sequencing.

Assembly statistics

Number of contigs	533,782
Assembly size (Mbp)	701
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	933
# contig > 1000 bp	180,950
# contig > 10000 bp	5,056
Largest contig (bp)	128,859
Smallest contig (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.9
N50 (bp)	2,830
L50	62,992
Ns (%)	0
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	965 [67.0%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	831 [57.7%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	134 [9.3%]

Fragmented BUSCOs	229 [15.9%]
Missing BUSCOs	246 [17.1%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

Any analyses involving data are included in this data usage policy, including annotation of genes, identification of sets of genomic features such as genes, gene families, regulatory elements, repeat structures, GC content, etc., and whole-genome comparisons of regions of among-species conservation. Also included are uses of the genome data as a reference for transcriptomic analyses (RNA seq, bisulfite seq, chip seq or similar). Interested parties are encouraged to contact the principal investigator if they wish to discuss the possibility of collaborative publication of such analyses.

The data may be freely downloaded and used by all who respect the restrictions in the previous paragraphs. In the period before the peer-reviewed journal publication the assembly and raw sequence reads should not be redistributed or repackaged without permission of Richard Buggs.

Once moved to unreserved status, the data will be freely available for any subsequent use.

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[Version 0.2 Scaffolds](#)

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Fraxinus pennsylvanica genome assembly [accession PE_00248]

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* [accession PE_00248], assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper, using materials provided by Jennifer Koch (USDA Forest Service). The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 23rd February 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 41x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters, incorporating data from mate-pair libraries with 3kb and 10kb insert sizes. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	555,484
Assembly size (Mbp)	902.5
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	893
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	74,643
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	20,214
Largest scaffold (bp)	524,151
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	33.2
N50 (bp)	18,659
L50	11,707
Ns (%)	11.4
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,266 [87.8%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,045 [72.6%]

Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	221 [15.3%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	42 [2.9%]
Missing BUSCOs	132 [9.2%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

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Version 0.2 Assembly

This version includes 800bp insert libraries and was assembled in 2018 by Josiah Seaman using the same pipeline and methodology. The new assemblies have higher contiguity, however annotations from v0.1 assemblies are not compatible with v0.2 coordinates. Other than the the additional sequence library all other sequence sources and methods are identical.

[Download v0.2 Assembly](#)

[v0.2 Annotation](#)

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Fraxinus pennsylvanica genome assembly [accession PE_48]

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* [accession PE_48], assembled by Laura Kelly. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 4th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 49x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for a library made from total genomic DNA, with an approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. No scaffolding or gap filling has been performed.

Assembly statistics

Number of contigs	715,871
Assembly size (Mbp)	761
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	868
# contig > 1000 bp	199,534
# contig > 10000 bp	3,317
Largest contig (bp)	104,414
Smallest contig (bp)	200
GC (%)	37.7
N50 (bp)	2,079
L50	88,850
Ns (%)	0
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	915 [63.5%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	791 [54.9%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	124 [8.6%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	214 [14.9%]
Missing BUSCOs	311 [21.6%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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Fraxinus platypoda genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus platypoda*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 12th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus platypoda* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 55x on the Illumina HiSeq platform. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	237,163
Assembly size (Mbp)	610.9
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	857
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	103,173
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	14,946
Largest scaffold (bp)	181,318
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.5
N50 (bp)	7,689
L50	22,689
Ns (%)	0.1
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,241 [86.2%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,028 [71.4%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	213 [14.8%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	86 [6%]
Missing BUSCOs	113 [7.8%]

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Fraxinus quadrangulata genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus quadrangulata*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 23rd February 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus quadrangulata* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 56x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters, incorporating data from mate-pair libraries with 3kb and 10kb insert sizes. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	175,641
Assembly size (Mbp)	692.9
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	765
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	32,861
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	13,558
Largest scaffold (bp)	394,910
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	31.18
N50 (bp)	50,545
L50	3,889
Ns (%)	8
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,328 [92.2%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,069 [74.2%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	259 [18.0%]

Fragmented BUSCOs	35 [2.4%]
Missing BUSCOs	77 [5.3%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

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Once moved to unreserved status, the data will be freely available for any subsequent use.

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Fraxinus sieboldiana genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus sieboldiana*, assembled by Laura Kelly. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 4th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus sieboldiana* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 44x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for a library made from total genomic DNA, with an approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. No scaffolding or gap filling has been performed.

Assembly statistics

Number of contigs	709,960
Assembly size (Mbp)	745
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	998
# contig > 1000 bp	193,339
# contig > 10000 bp	3,026
Largest contig (bp)	74,949
Smallest contig (bp)	200
GC (%)	36.21
N50 (bp)	1,987
L50	90,195
Ns (%)	0
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	901 [62.6%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	770 [53.5%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	131 [9.1%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	232 [16.1%]
Missing BUSCOs	307 [21.3%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/record/PRJEB20151). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

[Proceed to data download Version 0.1 assembly](#)

For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

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Fraxinus uhdei genome assembly

We have made available here the preliminary genome assembly of *Fraxinus uhdei*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data are as yet unpublished. If you want to publish any analysis of these data you must either wait until we have published them in a journal, or contact Richard Buggs to negotiate a co-authored paper.

Released on 12th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus uhdei* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 51x (but see update below) on the Illumina HiSeq platform. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Update 14th August 2017: a recent C-value estimate (generated by Alan Whittmore and colleagues at the US National Arboretum) indicates that the individual used for genome sequencing is a hexaploid; the estimated genome size in the table below has been updated to reflect this new C-value and the genome coverage is now estimated to be c. 18x.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	754,045
Assembly size (Mbp)	757.8
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	c. 2873
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	171,284
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	5,848
Largest scaffold (bp)	196,289
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.6
N50 (bp)	2,413
L50	71,645
Ns (%)	0.07
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,121 [77.8%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	971 [67.4%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	150 [10.4%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	124 [8.6%]
Missing BUSCOs	195 [13.5%]

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

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conservation. Also included are uses of the genome data as a reference for transcriptomic analyses (RNA seq, bisulfite seq, chip seq or similar). Interested parties are encouraged to contact the the principal investigator if they wish to discuss the possibility of collaborative publication of such analyses.

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Fraxinus velutina genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus velutina*, assembled by Laura Kelly. The v0.1 assembly and data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 4th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus velutina* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 48x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for a library made from total genomic DNA, with an approximate average insert size of 500bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. No scaffolding or gap filling has been performed.

Assembly statistics

Number of contigs	466,020
Assembly size (Mbp)	652
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	971
# contig > 1000 bp	170,053
# contig > 10000 bp	4,669
Largest contig (bp)	129,063
Smallest contig (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.9
N50 (bp)	2,997
L50	57,053
Ns (%)	0
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	987 [68.5%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	851 [59.1%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	136 [9.4%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	210 [14.6%]
Missing BUSCOs	243 [16.9%]

For the v0.1 assembly, DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/record/PRJEB20151). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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For the v0.2 assembly, the following applies:

As a public service, preliminary sequences of this genome are being made available before scientific publication. The purpose of this policy is to balance the desire that the ash genomes be made available to the scientific community as soon as possible with the reasonable expectation that the group responsible for the sequencing will publish their results in peer reviewed journals without concerns about potential pre-emption by other groups that did not directly participate in the effort.

These pre-publication data are preliminary and may contain errors. The goal of our policy is that early release should enable the progress of science. By accessing these data, you agree not to submit to scientific journals any articles containing analyses of these data prior to peer-reviewed journal publication by us and our collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.

Any analyses involving data are included in this data usage policy, including annotation of genes, identification of sets of genomic features such as genes, gene families, regulatory elements, repeat structures, GC content, etc., and whole-genome comparisons of regions of among-species conservation. Also included are uses of the genome data as a reference for transcriptomic analyses (RNA seq, bisulfite seq, chip seq or similar). Interested parties are encouraged to contact the principal investigator if they wish to discuss the possibility of collaborative publication of such analyses.

The data may be freely downloaded and used by all who respect the restrictions in the previous paragraphs. In the period before the peer-reviewed journal publication the assembly and raw sequence reads should not be redistributed or repackaged without permission of Richard Buggs.

Once moved to unreserved status, the data will be freely available for any subsequent use.

By downloading these data you are agreeing to the terms outlined above.

Version 0.2 Assembly

This version includes 800bp insert libraries and was assembled in 2018 by Josiah Seaman using the same pipeline and methodology. The new assemblies have higher contiguity, however annotations from v0.1 assemblies are not compatible with v0.2 coordinates. Other than the the additional sequence library all other sequence sources and methods are identical.

[Download v0.2 Assembly](#)

[v0.2 Annotation](#)

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Fraxinus xanthoxyloides genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus xanthoxyloides*, assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 11th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus xanthoxyloides* was sequenced to a depth of approximately 39x on the Illumina NextSeq and HiSeq platforms. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie ±40%). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	316,576
Assembly size (Mbp)	622.8
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	c.862
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	124,019
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	11,332
Largest scaffold (bp)	256,870
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.6
N50 (bp)	5,552
L50	30,973
Ns (%)	0.12
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,105 [76.7%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	973 [67.6%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	132 [9.2%]
Fragmented BUSCOs	153 [10.6%]
Missing BUSCOs	182 [12.6%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/record/PRJEB20151). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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Fraxinus sp. 1973-6204 genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus* sp. 1973-6204 (previously labelled as *Fraxinus bungeana*), assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 12th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus* sp. 1973-6204 was sequenced to a depth of approximately 58x on the Illumina HiSeq platform. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Update 27th April 2020: the species name has been changed from *Fraxinus bungeana* to *Fraxinus* sp. 1973-6204 following redetermination of the individual used for sequencing.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	550,497
Assembly size (Mbp)	926.4
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	1021
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	213,947
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	11,534
Largest scaffold (bp)	130,586
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.9
N50 (bp)	4,220
L50	59,815
Ns (%)	0.12
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,119 [77.7%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	951 [66%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	168 [11.7%]

Fragmented BUSCOs	152 [10.6%]
Missing BUSCOs	169 [11.7%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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Fraxinus sp. D2006-0159 genome assembly

We have made available here the genome assembly of *Fraxinus* sp. D2006-0159 (previously labelled as *Fraxinus chinensis*), assembled by Laura Kelly and Endymion Cooper. These data were published in May 2020 in *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; the paper can be accessed [here](#).

If referring to this assembly please cite:

Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>

Released on 12th April 2017. The genome of *Fraxinus* sp. D2006-0159 was sequenced to a depth of approximately 47x on the Illumina HiSeq platform. Paired reads for libraries made from total genomic DNA, with approximate average insert sizes of 300bp, 500bp and 800bp, were adapter trimmed and length and quality filtered. De novo assembly of the filtered read pairs, with a minimum read length of 50 nt, was conducted in the CLC Genomics Workbench under the following parameter settings: automatic optimization of word (k-mer) size; maximum size of bubble to try to resolve=5000; minimum contig length=200bp. As total genomic DNA was sequenced and assembled, contigs in the assembly include those that originate from the organellar genomes, as well as those from the nuclear genome. The assembly contained a single contig representing the Illumina PhiX control library; this contig was removed from the assembly. Assembled contigs were joined to form scaffolds using SSPACE (version 3.0) with default parameters. Library insert lengths were specified with a broad error range (ie $\pm 40\%$). Gaps in the SSPACE scaffolds were filled using GapCloser (version 1.12) with default parameters. The average library insert lengths were specified using the estimates produced by SSPACE during scaffolding.

Update 27th April 2020: the species name has been changed from *Fraxinus chinensis* to *Fraxinus* sp. D2006-0159 following redetermination of the individual used for sequencing.

Assembly statistics

Number of scaffolds	349,614
Assembly size (Mbp)	704.6
Estimated genome size (Mbp)	930
# scaffolds > 1000 bp	144,692
# scaffolds > 10000 bp	12,682
Largest scaffold (bp)	184,367
Smallest scaffold (bp)	200
GC (%)	34.3
N50 (bp)	5,515
L50	35,317
Ns (%)	0.11
Complete BUSCOs [% searched]	1,183 [82.2%]
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,006 [69.9%]
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	177 [12.3%]

Fragmented BUSCOs	126 [8.8%]
Missing BUSCOs	131 [9.1%]

DNA read files can be accessed through our European Nucleotide Archive study accession [PRJEB20151](#). The assembly file can be downloaded using the link below.

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Tools

Tools available for data analysis

[BLAST](#) - search Ash genomes (N.B. select "BATG-0.5-CLCbioSSPACE" for the published version of the *F.excelisior* genome)

[JBrowse](#) - view preliminary annotations

The annotation tracks under display are:

- "CLC_annotations" is derived from a mapping of RNA reads in the CLC Genomics Workbench. The data for this was pooled from five different tissues - leaves from the sequenced individual and its mother tree, as well as flowers, roots, and cambium from the mother tree.
- "Maker_repeats" is an intermediate output from the annotation pipeline Maker. It was trained by feeding the output of the CEGMA analysis into SNAP, which produced a Hidden Markov Model that was used in Maker. Repetitive regions and ab-initio predicted genes are visible.
- "Cambium_transcriptome" displays genes identified in the cambium tissue of the mother tree.
- "Flower_transcriptome" displays genes identified in the flower tissue of the mother tree.
- "Leaf-mother_transcriptome" displays genes identified in the leaf tissue of the mother tree.
- "Root_transcriptome" displays genes identified in the root tissue of the mother tree.
- "Leaf-selfed_transcriptome" displays genes identified in leaf tissue of the selfed tree (the individual for which we have provided a [genome sequence](#)).

The five 'tissue' transcriptomes were all produced using the Transcript Discovery plugin in the CLC Genomics Workbench. This tool uses a mapping of RNA-seq reads against the reference genome to predict the location and structure of transcripts. Reads were then mapped back to predicted transcripts and any genes with less than 5x coverage were removed. Transcript structure information of a gene can be viewed in a new window by clicking on the annotation and scrolling down to 'Subfeatures'. If a gene has more than one transcript, these will be listed as XXX.1, XXX.2, XXX.3 etc. (e.g. gene 850 in Cambium_transcriptome consists of two transcripts; 850.1 and 850.2). The lengths and positions of all introns and exons can also be viewed in this window.

How to navigate in JBrowse

From "**Available Tracks**" on the left hand side, drag the tracks of interest onto the main panel to activate it (or double-click on the track label).

Zoom in and out using the magnifying glasses in the middle of the tool bar.

Move along the length of a sequence by dragging the **red sliding window** at the very top, by hitting the respective arrows in the tool bar, or by moving the main panel directly.

To view a **different scaffold**, just type its name in the white panel in the tool bar and hit "Go" (or press enter).

For more information visit the [JBrowse webpage](#) or hit the "**?Help**" button in the upper right corner of the browser interface.

Please note that use of these tools and the data therein is subject to our [data usage policy](#) which was agreed upon entry to this site.

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Publications

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- Kelly, L.J., Plumb, W.J., Carey, D.W. et al. Convergent molecular evolution among ash species resistant to the emerald ash borer. *Nat Ecol Evol* 4, 1116–1128 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3>
- Tim L. R. Coker, Jiří Rozsypálek, Anne Edwards, Tony P. Harwood, Louise A. Butfoy, Richard J. A. Buggs (2018) Estimating mortality rates of European ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) under the ash dieback (*Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*) epidemic. *Plants People Planet* (in press)
- Elizabeth S. A. Sollars and Richard J. A. Buggs (2018) Genome-wide epigenetic variation among ash trees differing in susceptibility to a fungal disease. *BMC Genomics* 19:502
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-018-4874-8>
- Elizabeth S. A. Sollars, Andrea L. Harper, Laura J. Kelly, Christine M. Sambles, Ricardo H. Ramirez-Gonzalez, David Swarbreck, Gemy Kaithakottil, Endymion D. Cooper, Cristobal Uauy, Lenka Havlickova, Gemma Worswick, David J. Studholme, Jasmin Zohren, Deborah L. Salmon, Bernardo J. Clavijo, Yi Li, Zhesi He, Alison Fellgett, Lea Vig McKinney, Lene Rostgaard Nielsen, Gerry C. Douglas, Erik Dahl Kjær, J. Allan Downie, David Boshier, Steve Lee, Jo Clark, Murray Grant, Ian Bancroft, Mario Caccamo and Richard J. A. Buggs (2016) Genome sequence and genetic diversity of European ash trees. *Nature* 541: 212–216 [doi:10.1038/nature20786](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature20786)
- Harper, A.L., et al. (2016). Molecular for tolerance of European Ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) to dieback disease identified using Associative Transcriptomics. *Scientific Reports*, 6, Article number: 19335. <http://www.nature.com/articles/srep19335>

Talks

- “The Future for English Woodlands” Conference organised by The Central Association of Agricultural Valuers and The Royal Forestry Society, 30 Oct 2018, The National Memorial Arboretum, Staffordshire
- “Plant Health Conference”, The Earth Trust, Oxfordshire, 17th Oct 2018
- Shirley Sherwood Gallery, RBG Kew, 10th Oct 2018
- Garnet Meeting, University of York, 19 Sept 2018
- University of Birmingham, 29 March 2018
- Forestry Commission’s “SE & London Tree Health Event 2018” attended by 130 tree health professionals, 12 Feb 2018
- Dissemination event for the Tree Health and Plant Biosecurity Initiative, at the Radisson Blu Grafton, London, 7 Feb 2018
- Presentation to Ian Boyd, Defra Chief Scientific Advisor, Nobel House, Westminster, 24 Oct 2017
- Defra Ash Dieback Health and Safety Taskgroup, Nobel House, Westminster, 11 May 2017
- BSCB/BSDB/Genetics Society Spring Meeting, University of Warwick 2 – 5 April 2017
- UK Plant Science 2015, Harper Adams University 14-15 Apr 2015
- Forest Research Northern Research Station Seminar 18 Mar 2015
- Defra/BBSRC Ash Dieback Oversight Group meeting, Nobel House, 27 Feb 2015

- Department of Plant Sciences, University of Cambridge, Departmental Seminar 19 Feb 2015
- Northeastern Forestry University, Harbin, China 14 Aug 2015
- International Plant & Animal Genome XXIII San Diego, CA, USA. [PAG XXII](#), January 10-14, 2015. Sollars ESA, Kelly L, Clavijo B, Swarbreck D, Zohren J, Boshier D, Clark J, Joecker A, Caccamo M, Buggs RJA, (2014). "[The genome of Fraxinus excelsior \(European Ash\)](#)".
- International Plant & Animal Genome XXII San Diego, CA, USA. [PAG XXII](#), January 11-15, 2014. Sollars ESA, Zohren J, Boshier D, Clark J, Joecker A, Buggs RJA, (2014). "[Sequencing the genome of Fraxinus excelsior \(European Ash\)](#)".

Posters

(click on the images to view the PDF)

- 35th [New Phytologist Symposium](#). The genomes of forest tree: new frontiers of forest biology. Boston, MA, USA. June 16-17 2015

Genome sequencing of *Fraxinus* species to identify loci relevant to ash dieback and emerald ash borer

ESA Sollars^{1,2}, LJ Kelly¹, D Swarbreck¹, B Clavijo¹, C Kalkbrenner¹, J Zohren¹, D Boshier¹, J Clark³, S Lee⁴, J Koch⁵, J E Carlson⁶, E D Kiper⁷, LR Nielsen⁸, W Crowther¹, SJ Rossiter¹, A Joecker¹, S Ayling¹, M Caccamo¹, RJA Buggs¹

Threats to ash trees
The Emerald Ash Borer (EAB) and other invasive species are causing significant damage to ash trees in the UK. EAB is particularly threatening to ash trees in the UK and is expected to spread to other ash tree species in the presence of ash dieback.

Fraxinus excelsior reference genome
We assembled and annotated the genome of one subspecies of ash from England. We are working on a reference genome map to improve our understanding of the genome.

European diversity panel
We have sequenced 100 genomes of 17 *F. excelsior* from across Europe. This data is available to the research community.

Genus-wide genome sequencing
To provide insight into the genome of other *F. excelsior* species we are sequencing the genomes of several other species in the genus *Fraxinus*.

Screening for susceptibility
We are conducting genome-wide screens of the susceptibility of *Fraxinus* species to ash dieback and the emerald ash borer. This research suggests that some species, especially those from the east Asian range, may be more susceptible. We are working to test the level of susceptibility in the context of the UK. We currently have 100 genomes of *F. excelsior* from across Europe. We are currently sequencing 100 genomes of *F. excelsior* from across Europe. We are currently sequencing 100 genomes of *F. excelsior* from across Europe.

A novel phylogenomic method for candidate gene identification
We aim to build phylogenetic trees for thousands of genes in the genus *Fraxinus*. This will allow us to identify genes that are important for ash dieback and EAB. We are working to test the level of susceptibility in the context of the UK. We currently have 100 genomes of *F. excelsior* from across Europe. We are currently sequencing 100 genomes of *F. excelsior* from across Europe.

- International Plant & Animal Genome XXII San Diego, CA, USA. [PAG XXII](#), January 11-15, 2014.

AND:

- 47th Population Genetics Group Meeting, Bath, UK. [PopGroup47](#), January 7-10, 2014.

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Funding

We would like to thank the following funding bodies for supporting our work on The British Ash Tree Genome Project:

Living with Environmental Change: Tree Health and Plant Biosecurity Initiative, funded jointly by a grant from BBSRC, Defra, ESRC, the Forestry Commission, NERC and the Scottish Government.

The Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)

[INTERCROSSING](#), a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Initial Training Network (ITN) and FRAXIFAM, a Marie Skłodowska-Curie International Fellowship to Endymion Cooper under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 660003).

Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) and The Genome Analysis Centre

The Erica Waltraud Albrecht Endowment Fund

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